

An integrated approach based on ecological and geo-environmental indicators for the spatio-temporal monitoring of desertification: The case of the Skoura oasis (Morocco)

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Abstract

The Skoura oasis, located in the Ouarzazate region of southern Morocco, represents a fragile agro-ecosystem increasingly affected by land degradation processes. This study aims to analyze the spatio-temporal dynamics of desertification in the oasis from 1984 to 2024, in light of climate variability and anthropogenic pressures. An integrated approach combining remote sensing data and environmental indicators is adopted to characterize changes in vegetation and soil conditions. High-resolution satellite imagery from Pléiades 2023 and time series data from the Landsat (5, 7, 8) and Sentinel-2 missions are processed using object-based image analysis and segmentation techniques. Three key indicators are employed: the Modified Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (MSAVI), surface albedo, and the Sand Fraction Index (SFI). These indicators are integrated to construct a Desertification Monitoring Index (DMI) within the Google Earth Engine platform. Results reveal that in 1984, 24.3% of the oasis area was already classified as highly desertified, particularly in the eastern, southern, and central zones. A slight improvement was observed by 1996, with the desertified surface decreasing to 8.6%. However, a renewed intensification occurred between 1996 and 2010, especially in areas dominated by date palms and olive groves. From 2010 to 2024, desertification progressed further, marked by significant vegetation loss. The findings highlight the persistence and aggravation of land degradation over four decades. The study demonstrates the value of integrated remote sensing approaches for monitoring desertification and supports the need for adaptive strategies to ensure the sustainable management of oasis ecosystems.

Key words: Agro-ecosystem, arid zone, Desertification Monitoring Index (DMI), remote sensing, spectral indices

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1. Introduction

Over the decades, Morocco, has been one of the countries most affected by desertification (Labbaci and Bouchaou 2021). It is, moreover, made up of 92% dry areas (arid, semi-arid and sub-humid) (Roose et al. 2010), It is characterised by predominantly arid and semi-arid climatic variations, especially in the southern regions (Ait Houssa et al. 2017). The country lies on the coast between the humid (temperate) biome to the north and the desert regions and the Sahel to the

south (Meliho et al. 2024). Around 15% of the country's territory is occupied by oases, which cover a total area of 107,324 km² where 98% is desert land and 2% is used for agriculture (Ait El Mokhtar et al. 2019). They constitute an oasis corridor along the Oued Draa and the depressions (Lamqadem et al. 2017). It plays an essential role in combating desertification, which is currently on the increase in the south-eastern part of the country (Eddahby et al. 2019).

The Skoura oasis, selected as a case study for the development of a desertification monitoring index based on key variables sensitive to land degradation (MSAVI, albedo, and SFI), exemplifies the inherent vulnerability of oasis ecosystems to climate change. Located upstream of the Draa Valley, the Skoura palm grove, like many other Moroccan oases, has experienced severe vegetation degradation over the past 40 years (Aziz and Elquaoumi 2016). This analysis highlights the land transformations driven by two major agricultural crises that have affected the Skoura oasis. The first, in the early 1980s, marked a pivotal turning point in the degradation of the palm grove (Sedra 2015). The second, observed over the past few decades, is part of an extended drought period that has signaled a new critical phase in desertification (Agrisud International 2004).

The innovative aspect of this study lies in the application of a desertification monitoring approach based on object segmentation from high-resolution images, enabling a long-term monitoring of agro-ecological and environmental land conditions in Moroccan oases under arid Saharan climate. Unlike Zongfan et al. (2022), who relied on pixel-based and short-term analyses, this method captures spatially coherent land units and their temporal dynamics. In contrast to Moumane et al. (2022) and Amraoui et al. (2022), who limited their analyses to a single vegetation index and classification by maximum likelihood, our approach integrates multiple biophysical indices that better reflect land conditions. Similarly, while Karmaoui et al. (2023) focused solely on groundwater and salinity, and Rayne et al. (2023) examined desertification in relation to irrigation systems, the present study goes further by incorporating land stability metrics and correlating desertification dynamics with climatic data. This provides a more comprehensive and ecologically grounded framework to understand the interplay between climate change and desertification processes in fragile oasis ecosystems.

Desertification leads to soil erosion (Ferreira et al. 2022) and vegetation degradation (Filchev 2020; Shen et al. 2022), threatening not only biodiversity and people's living environment, but also limiting the sustainable development of the local ecological environment and social economy (Dharumarajan et al. 2018; Kalyan et al. 2021; Prodanova 2021; Zongfan et al. 2022). Desertification monitoring, particularly in severely affected areas, is essential for understanding the desertification process and implementing early warning measures to prevent this phenomenon (Ghebregabher et al. 2019). As an alternative to often time-consuming and labour-intensive field experiments, remote sensing offers an effective approach for monitoring desertification (Mutti et al. 2020; Yu et al. 2020; Zongfan et al. 2022).

Many remote sensing indices have been proposed to reflect desertification (Liu et al. 2018; Zhao et al. 2020), as this phenomenon modifies satellite-derived vegetation indices (VI) and albedo, affecting vegetation cover and surface moisture (La et al. 2019; Zongfan et al. 2022). For example, a desertification difference index, calculated using the normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) and albedo, has been used in many studies to reveal desertification (Wu

et al. 2014; Liu et al. 2018; Zou et al. 2019). However, NDVI is sensitive to the signature of the soil background, which may introduce a bias in semi-arid areas with less than 50% vegetation cover (John et al. 2018). In contrast, the modified soil-adjusted vegetation index (MSAVI) broadens the dynamic range of vegetation signals and reduces the influence of soil background (Wei et al. 2018).

Many studies highlight, MSAVI, which has a numerical range between -1 and 1, differs from NDVI by incorporating a dynamic adjustment factor. This factor varies according to the actual level of vegetation cover, allowing optimal reduction of noise from the ground (Wei et al. 2018). When vegetation cover is high, MSAVI behaves similarly to NDVI. However, when vegetation cover is low, MSAVI is more effective at monitoring vegetation condition. This makes it a particularly suitable tool for identifying vegetation in low-density environments, such as semi-arid areas, where it outperforms NDVI in terms of efficiency (Li et al. 2017). Therefore, Wu et al. (2014) replaced the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) with the Modified Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (MSAVI) to develop a desertification index combining albedo. This approach demonstrated that the modified desertification index allows for more accurate monitoring of desertification compared to previously used indices.

Meng (2005) proposed the sandy feature index (SFI), based on the differences in spectral features between sandy and non-sandy land, with an SFI value > 0 . Zongfan et al. (2022) compared raster SFI images with synthetic true-colour images and found that sandy areas had high SFI values, while water bodies, croplands and forests had low values. The SFI was therefore used to extract sandy areas with satisfactory results. However, existing research shows that, during the evolution of desertification, vegetation cover, surface albedo and the degree of sandiness of land are all influenced by this process (Wang et al. 2014; Chen et al. 2021; Zongfan et al. 2022). Consequently, limiting oneself to the vegetation index and albedo, or focusing solely on the SFI, does not accurately reflect the real level of desertification.

In this study, we chose the Skoura oasis as an example to develop a Desertification Monitoring Index (DMI) by integrating three key variables sensitive to land degradation: MSAVI, albedo, and SFI. Instead of using a simple linear weighting approach, the combination was performed through the spatial distance method, which measures the Euclidean distance between each pixel value and the reference point that represents the minimal desertification condition (defined by the minimum value of MSAVI and the maximum values of albedo and SFI). This approach allows the three indicators to be objectively normalized in a multidimensional space and jointly contribute to the DMI, where higher distances indicate higher desertification severity. The approaches used combine oriented object analysis with spectral based indices. Initially, homogeneous objects were delineated through image segmentation performed with the SNIC (Simple Non-Iterative Clustering) algorithm on a high-resolution Pléiades image (0.5 m). Within these objects the three indices were yearly analysed over a period from 1984 to 2024. The integrated index (DMI) makes it possible to detect areas affected by desertification and capture its dynamic.

The DMI index was classified using Jenks' natural breaks method, allowing for the optimal grouping of similar values while maximizing the differences between classes. This classification aims to determine the levels of desertification, detect interannual changes, and assess the stabilization of land within the

Skoura oasis during the study period, in order to analyse the impact of climatic data on the evolution of desertification in the area. This approach also underscores the critical importance of employing remote sensing–derived indicators to monitor ecosystem changes (Nedkov et al. 2021).

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study area

The Skoura palm grove is located in the province of Ouarzazate, in south-east Morocco, around 40 kilometres east of the town of Ouarzazate (Fig. 1). It lies in the Dades valley, on the road between Ouarzazate and Tinghir, in the Draa–Tafilalet region. The Middle Draa Valley Catchment Area (MDVC) is an oasis region in south-east Morocco. It borders the Sahara desert and is highly vulnerable to drought and desertification. The Draa Valley (locally known as Oued Draa) rises in the High Atlas Mountains and flows south towards the Sahara Desert, supporting a 200-kilometre belt of six oases (Mezquita, Tinzouline, Ternata, Fezouta, Ktaoua and M’hamid from north to south) (Moumane et al.

Figure 1. Geographical location of the study area. **A** Ouarzazate Province in Morocco **B** position of the Skoura oasis within Ouarzazate Province **C** Pleiades satellite image of the study area.

2022). The Draa river is controlled by the Mansour Eddahbi dam located near the town of Ouarzazate, with a total average annual discharge of 120,000,000 cubic metres. These discharges recharge the valley's alluvial aquifers as well as the limited surface water used for irrigation (Moumane et al. 2022).

2.2. Data

Three sources of satellite data were selected to enrich the analysis (Table 1). Firstly, the Landsat archive, made up of optical images dating back to 1972, makes it possible to construct a time series over a 40-year period. This makes it possible to track changes in vegetation and the state of desertification of the land from the start of the wet season to the present day. Secondly, images from the Sentinel-2 satellites have been used to calculate and produce rasters representing various geo-environmental indicators, taking advantage of their high spatial resolution of 10 metres. These images, with their spectral resolution of 13 bands covering the optical and near-infrared ranges, provide high-quality multispectral information for detailed analysis of Earth surface features. They are specially designed to monitor the environment, vegetation, soil and water resources, making them an essential tool for studying environmental dynamics and land degradation processes. The third source is the Pleiades images, whose spatial resolution enables a detailed assessment of the state of the oasis agro-ecosystem (Skoura oasis).

Table 1. The data used in our study.

Satellite	Usage period	Spatial resolution	Main spectral bands	Interest of use
Landsat 5	1984–2000	30 m (MS), 120 m (Thermal)	Blue, Green, Red, NIR, SWIR 1, SWIR 2, Thermal	Used for calculating the MSAVI, SFI, and Albedo indices to monitor and analyze the evolution of desertification in the Skoura palm grove over a temporal series.
Landsat 7	2000–2013	30 m (MS), 15 m (Panchromatic), 60 m (Thermal)	Blue, Green, Red, NIR, SWIR 1, SWIR 2, Thermal, Panchromatic	
Landsat 8	2013–2015	30 m (MS), 15 m (Panchromatic)	Coastal Aerosol, Blue, Green, Red, NIR, SWIR 1, SWIR 2, Panchromatic, Cirrus	
Sentinel-2	2015–2024	10 m (RGB, NIR), 20 m (SWIR, Red Edge), 60 m (Cirrus, Water Vapor)	Aerosols, Blue, Green, Red, Red Edge 1–3, NIR, Narrow NIR, SWIR 1–2, Cirrus, Water Vapor	
Pleiades	2022	0.5 m (Panchromatic), 2 m (MS)	Blue, Green, Red, NIR, Panchromatic	Very high-resolution data for precise mapping and segmentation of land features.

2.3. Methodology

The methodology for analyzing desertification in the Skoura oasis is based on several key steps aimed at assessing the evolution of desertification from 1984 to 2024 (Fig. 2). The first step involves the collection of satellite data (Landsat and Sentinel) covering the study period, as well as high-resolution Pleiades imagery. Next, the geo-environmental indicators required for the study are cal-

culated using Google Earth Engine, such as the MSAVI (Modified Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index), SFI (Sandy Feature Index), and Albedo. Once these indices are obtained, a Desertification Monitoring Index (DMI) is calculated from the standardized values of these three indices. The DMI quantifies the degree of desertification for each segment (polygon) of the area. These segments are obtained through object segmentation on the Pleiades image using the SNIC (Simple Non-Iterative Clustering) algorithm with its five parameters (size, compactness, connectivity, neighborhood size, and seeds), which isolate different geographic entities (homogeneous polygons). A zonal statistical analysis is then performed for each segment, enabling the determination of the average desertification degree for each polygon across the time series.

The analysis of desertification evolution is then carried out. It aims to identify the levels of desertification, interannual changes, and the stability of the land within the Skoura oasis during the study period. Once this analysis is completed, a correlation is established between the evolution of desertification and climatic factors. Finally, the results of this analysis are validated using cross-validation methods and compared with field data.

Figure 2. Methodological framework.

2.4. Object delineation: automatic segmentation

Google Earth Engine (GEE), a cloud-based geospatial analysis platform, enables image segmentation by evaluating spatial relationships among neighboring pixels and merging them into homogeneous polygons that represent meaningful units of the oasis landscape.

In this study, five key parameters were optimized to achieve the most appropriate segmentation of the case study area using the SNIC (Simple Non-Iterative Clustering) algorithm implemented in Google Earth Engine. These param-

eters control both the size and the homogeneity of the generated objects and are described as follows (Qu et al. 2021): 1) Size (seed spacing): defines the distance between initial seed points. Smaller values generate a larger number of seeds and produce finer, smaller segments, whereas larger values result in coarser segmentation with bigger polygons. 2) Compactness: regulates the balance between spatial proximity and spectral similarity during pixel aggregation. Higher values promote compact and regular segment shapes, while lower values allow more elongated or spectrally driven segments. 3) Connectivity: specifies whether pixels are connected through 4-neighbour or 8-neighbour relationships, thereby determining the spatial continuity of the resulting segments. 4) Neighbourhood size: sets the local search window around each seed point that is considered during the clustering process. Larger neighbourhoods improve smoothness and stability of the segmentation but require higher computational resources. 5) Seeds (optional): allows the use of custom seed points instead of automatically generated ones. This option is useful when prior knowledge or reference data is available to guide the segmentation process.

The SNIC algorithm performs object-based image segmentation by initiating a set of seed points and iteratively growing clusters based on spectral similarity and spatial proximity. Unlike iterative clustering methods, SNIC is computationally efficient and produces spatially coherent segments with well-defined boundaries, making it particularly suitable for high-resolution imagery such as

Figure 3. Extracted part of the interest object segmentation of the Skoura palm grove based on the Pleiades image. **1** terrain with dense vegetation, non-desertified **2** terrain occupied by date palms with low desertification **3** terrain with olive trees and degraded soil **4** terrain with very sparse vegetation and highly desertified soil.

Pleiades. These parameters enable the refinement of segmentation to meet the specific requirements of the analysis by adjusting segment size, homogeneity, and consistency. The use of SNIC ensures that the resulting polygons reflect meaningful and homogeneous land-cover units, which are essential for accurately mapping land degradation dynamics in the oasis landscape. Fig. 3 illustrates specific areas within the oasis agro-ecosystem, identified using the 2022 processed Pléiades image. These areas highlight different categories of land desertification within the oasis.

2.5. Spectral indices: MSAVI, Albedo, and SFI indices

Desertification is characterized by a decline in vegetation cover, reduced soil moisture, high albedo and the expansion of sandy surfaces. To assess this phenomenon, three primary indicators were employed: the Modified Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index (MSAVI), which directly measures vegetation density; albedo, a critical factor in the Earth’s surface energy balance; and the Sand Feature Index (SFI), designed to identify land degradation level and analyze sand-dominated areas (Fig. 4).

MSAVI distinguishes itself from the NDVI by incorporating a dynamic adjustment factor that varies with actual vegetation cover, thereby minimizing soil-related noise (Wei et al. 2018). It is calculated using the formula (eq. 1):

$$MSAVI = \frac{2(NIR + 1) - \sqrt{(2NIR + 1)^2 - 8(NIR - R)}}{2} \quad (\text{eq. 1})$$

Figure 4. A Extract from the Pleiades image. With calculated spectral indices: B Albedo C MSAVI D SFI. Rectangles 1, 2, 3, and 4 correspond to the same plots mentioned earlier, used to assess the results.

Surface albedo, a key determinant of radiant energy absorption, plays a pivotal role in the radiative energy balance of the soil (Li et al. 2013). It is computed as (eq. 2):

$$Albedo = 0.356B + 0.13R + 0.373NIR + 0.085SWIR_1 + 0.072SWIR_2 - 0.0018 \quad (eq. 2)$$

SFI is a robust indicator for monitoring sandy areas due to its simplicity, ease of calculation, and practical extraction accuracy (Meng 2005). It is derived using the formula (eq. 3):

$$SFI = \frac{SWIR_1 - B}{200 - SWIR_2} \quad (eq. 3)$$

Where B, R, NIR, SWIR₁, and SWIR₂ represent reflectance in the blue, red, near-infrared, and mid-infrared bands, respectively. Notably, the magnitudes of these indices are not uniform and require standardization to ensure comparability, often achieved by scaling them to a standardized statistical range (eq. 4).

$$M = \frac{MSAVI - MSAVI_{min}}{MSAVI_{max} - MSAVI}$$

$$A = \frac{Albedo - Albedo_{min}}{Albedo_{max} - Albedo} \times 100\% \quad (eq. 4)$$

$$S = \frac{SFI - SFI_{min}}{SFI_{max} - SFI} \times 100\%$$

2.6. Identification and calculation of the DMI

The linear weighting method or the weighted geometric mean approach does not allow for a quantitative description of the relationship between the MSAVI (Modified Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index), albedo, and SFI (Soil Fertility Index) when integrating them to construct the Desertification Monitoring Index (DMI) (Xu et al. 2019). To overcome this limitation, an alternative approach based on Euclidean distance theory has been proposed (Mesquita et al. 2017) (Fig. 5). The Spatial Distance Index (SDI), introduced by Wei et al. (2018), represents an innovative composite index methodology for the evaluation of desertification processes. Grounded in spatial distance theory, the SDI model enables a more objective and accurate assessment of the contribution of various environmental indicators in diagnosing and quantifying desertification dynamics (Li et al. 2019; Guo and Wen 2020).

Figure 5. Schematic diagram of the principle for spatial distance method (Zongfan et al. 2022).

In this context, our study utilized the minimum value of MSAVI and the maximum values of albedo and SFI. The maximum values of albedo and SFI were considered to represent the points of minimal desertification severity. The distance between these minimal points and other points in space was then calculated (eq. 5). Consequently, the range of values for the DMI lies between 0 and $\sqrt{3}$, where a greater distance corresponds to a higher DMI value, indicating an elevated level of desertification (Fig. 6).

$$DMI = \sqrt{(M - Mmin)^2 + (A - Amax)^2 + (S - Smax)^2} \quad (\text{eq. 5})$$

Figure 6. DMI results from calculations based on the MSAVI, SFI, and Albedo indices. Rectangles 1, 2, 3, and 4 correspond to the same plots mentioned earlier, used to assess the results.

To assess desertification in the Skoura oasis, an in-depth analysis was conducted by combining historical data from the DMI spanning the period from 1984 to 2024 with polygons generated through object-based segmentation. Subsequently, a zonal statistics method was applied to assign an average DMI value to each polygon for each year of the study period. This approach enabled the integration of the spatial and temporal dynamics of desertification by linking multi-temporal satellite data with defined spatial units, thereby providing a precise understanding of the evolution of desertification at the local scale (Fig. 7).

Figure 7. Desertification Mapping Index (DMI) before and after applying the zonal statistical method. **A** segmentation **B** pixel-based DMI **C** overlay of segments and DMI **D** polygon-based DMI.

The Jenks Natural Breaks method, also referred to as the Goodness of Variance Fit (GVF) optimization method, relies on an iterative process of calculating the GVF. This process involves moving a value from the class with the largest deviations from the mean of the dataset to the class with the smallest deviations, continuing until the sum of deviations within the classes is minimized (Jiang 2013). In our study, this classification method was employed to categorize land areas (polygons) based on field survey data according to the degree of desertification as measured by the DMI.

2.7. Consideration of historical data on dual agrarian crises

The presentation of the results will focus on the years 1984, 1996, 2010, and 2024, which have been selected as key temporal reference points. This selection is grounded in prior research that highlights their relevance for understanding the evolution of the desertification process in the Skoura region. Over the study period, this region has experienced two major crises that have significantly impacted on its ecological and environmental systems.

In the early 1980s, the Skoura oasis experienced an intensification of desertification, posing a significant threat to the local ecosystem (Sedra 2015). This environmental degradation was primarily driven by a notable rise in temperatures and a decline in soil moisture (Ait-El-Mokhtar et al. 2021). These adverse climatic conditions led to the deterioration of agricultural land (Anjarne et al. 2005),

particularly those cultivated with species from the Rosaceae family, such as almond, fig, apricot, and apple trees, which require high levels of water and humidity (Agrisud International 2004; Ait-El-Mokhtar et al. 2021). This period thus marks the first major agrarian crisis to affect the Skoura oasis (Sedra 2015).

Following the 1980s, various adaptation strategies were implemented to mitigate the effects of desertification (Agrisud International 2004). This period is characterized by the introduction and widespread adoption of olive cultivation (Aziz and Elquaoumi 2016), along with the development of annual crops such as maize, alfalfa, and various grasses. Additionally, seasonal vegetables were introduced, including winter crops such as turnips and carrots, and summer crops such as tomatoes and zucchinis (Bihaoui et al. 2020). The primary objective of these efforts was to compensate for the gradual loss of plant species sensitive to arid conditions and to restore the fertility of agricultural land.

Since 2010, The region has entered a new phase of environmental degradation, as shown by multiple converging criteria indicating this trend (Fig. 8), marked by a significant reduction in the areas cultivated with date palms and olive trees (Sedra 2015). Date palms are increasingly affected by biotic threats, notably the Bayoud disease (Aziz and Elquaoumi 2016), while the multi-strata composition of the palm grove faces abiotic stresses such as drought (Sedra 2015), soil salinity (Ait-El-Mokhtar et al. 2021), and a growing scarcity of water. This water scarcity is largely attributed to decreased rainfall (Badraoui and Dahan 2011), an increased number of heatwave days (Driouech 2010), and the overexploitation of groundwater resources (Agovino et al. 2019). Annual crops, such as cereals, certain vegetables, and alfalfa have also experienced a notable decline due to the reduction of irrigated areas (Beraaouz et al. 2022). This period is thus characterized by a second agrarian crisis that has profoundly impacted the Skoura oasis.

Figure 8. Current composition of the Skoura palm grove and main natural phenomena reported in earlier studies. **A** multi-layered structure of the Skoura palm grove **B** olive tree affected by drought **C** gully erosion **D** visible traces of soil salinity **E** combined effects of Bayoud disease and drought on date palms.

2.8. Desertification trends

To analyze the interannual evolution of the DMI, a desertification variation index—referred to as the Desertification Interannual Change Index (DICI)—was calculated for each polygon within the study area, using a time series spanning from 1984 to 2024. This index quantifies the rate of change in desertification levels and was applied to assess fluctuations across three specific intervals:

1984–1996, 1996–2010, and 2010–2024. These periods are considered key milestones in the region’s ecosystem dynamics. This approach enables the identification of long-term trends in either the improvement or deterioration of desertification conditions in the Skoura oasis over the decades. The DICl is computed using the following formula (eq. 6):

$$DICl = \frac{Dx - Dy}{Dy} \tag{eq. 6}$$

Where: *Dy* represents the desertification level value from the initial year of the studied period, and *Dx* represents the desertification level value from the final year of the studied period. When $DICl < 0$, it indicates an improvement in the desertification status of the area; $DICl = 0$ signifies that the desertification status has remained unchanged; and $DICl > 0$ implies a deterioration in the desertification status of the area.

2.9. Stability index

The primary objective of this section of the study is to assess land stability in the face of desertification through statistical measures. By analyzing the variability of the DMI over the time series from 1984 to 2024, it is possible to identify the most stable areas as well as those that have been subjected to con-

Table 2. The statistical indicators used to assess land resilience to desertification in the Skoura oasis.

Statistical indicators	Equation and objective
Standard deviation (eq. 7)	$\sigma = \sqrt{(1/n) \sum (xi - \mu)^2} \tag{eq. 7}$ <p>To measure the dispersion of desertification level values around the mean. A low standard deviation indicates greater stability.</p>
Mean (eq. 8)	$\mu = (1/n) \sum xi \tag{eq. 8}$ <p>To determine the central tendency of the desertification level for each segment.</p>
Normalized mean (eq. 9)	$\mu_{norm} = \frac{(\mu - \min(\mu))}{(\max(\mu) - \min(\mu))} \tag{eq. 9}$ <p>To scale the mean values onto a normalized scale in order to compare the segments equitably.</p>
Coefficient of variation (eq. 10)	$CV = \sigma / \mu \tag{eq. 10}$ <p>To measure the relative variability of the desertification level while considering the scale of the values. A low coefficient value indicates temporal stability of the desertification level.</p>
Normalized coefficient of variation (eq. 11)	$CV_{norm} = \frac{(CV - \min(CV))}{(\max(CV) - \min(CV))} \tag{eq. 11}$ <p>This normalization facilitates the interpretation and classification of the segments.</p>
Stability Index (eq. 12)	$\text{Score} = \mu_{norm} + CV_{norm} \tag{eq. 12}$ <p>The different metrics were integrated into a single index to classify polygons according to their stability. Lower scores indicate higher stability and a more favorable environmental condition.</p>

tinuous desertification over an extended period. Multiple indicators were computed based on DMI values representing the level of desertification for each polygon analyzed over the 1984–2024 period (Table 2).

To ensure ecological relevance, the normalization and weighting of the DMI were designed to reflect both the average state of land conditions and their temporal variability. From an ecological perspective, the mean desertification level (μ) represents the long-term environmental status of each polygon, while the coefficient of variation (CV) captures its resilience or sensitivity to inter-annual fluctuations. Normalization (Eqs. 9 and 11) was applied to scale these metrics onto a common range, ensuring comparability between polygons with different absolute values by integrating the normalized mean and variability into a Stability Index (Eq. 12).

After classifying the stability index using Jenks Natural Breaks, the polygons (areas) with the lowest scores are identified as areas that have maintained the best environmental and vegetative conditions over time from 1984 to 2024. And the areas with higher values are identified as persistently desertified soils throughout the time series.

2.10. Correlation between desertification and climate factors

The Skoura Oasis remains a vulnerable and fragile ecosystem that can be altered by the effects of exogenous factors such as climate change, leading to warming and desertification (Ait-El-Mokhtar 2021; Behnassi et al. 2022). Between 1961 and 2008, the climate warming rate was 0.3°C per decade, and the highest recorded water deficits reached -84% in 2000 (Driouech 2010; Behnassi et al. 2022). The major droughts of the 1980s and 2000s, which dried up most of the khettaras in Skoura (Mahdane et al. 2011), led to the degradation of land in the oasis. The dual agrarian crisis (Sedra 2015) has a clear impact on the evolution of desertification in the oasis. The relationship between desertification levels and climatic factors was investigated by performing correlation analyses using temperature, precipitation, and soil moisture data. This approach enables the assessment of how variations in these climate variables potentially influence the spatial and temporal dynamics of desertification in the Skoura oasis.

Using Google Earth Engine (GEE), we extracted annual mean values of Land Surface Temperature (LST) in degrees Celsius from Landsat data over the entire study period (Todorova and Zhiyanski 2025). Annual precipitation averages, expressed in millimeters, were derived from CHIRPS data, while annual mean soil moisture values (m^3/m^3) were calculated using ECMWF/ERA5 data. These climatic indicators were then compared to the evolution of desertification classes within the scope of our study.

To assess the consistency between the spatio-temporal dynamics of desertification (non-desertification and severe desertification) in the Skoura oasis and certain climatic factors (land surface temperature (LST), annual precipitation, and soil moisture), a comparative approach was adopted based on binary classification of the variables (Chung et al. 2019; Kabanda 2024) over the period 1984–2024. The data were binarized into two classes (favourable or unfavourable) using the median as the threshold (Donges et al. 2016). Two similarity indicators were employed:

The coincidence rate is defined as the proportion of years during which two binary time series (e.g., percentage of non-desertified areas in Skoura vs. classified land surface temperature) exhibit the same value (0 or 1) (Keenan 1982). It is expressed by the following formula (eq. 13) (Donges et al. 2016):

$$\text{Coincidence}(A, B) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N 1(A_i = B_i) \quad (\text{eq. 13})$$

Where N represents the number of years considered. A value of 100% indicates a “perfect synchronization” between the classes, 50% corresponds to synchronization expected by chance, and 0% reflects complete opposition between the two series (Donges et al. 2016).

The Jaccard index, which quantifies the similarity between binary series (Koeneman and Cavanaugh 2022), was originally introduced by Jaccard (1912). It is widely used in ecology and remote sensing to compare asymmetric binary data (Podani 2021). It is expressed by the following formula (eq. 14)

$$J(A, B) = \frac{M_{11}}{M_{11} + M_{10} + M_{01}} \quad (\text{eq. 14})$$

Where M_{11} : number of years when both $A = 1$ and $B = 1$; M_{10} : $A = 1$, $B = 0$; M_{01} : $A = 0$, $B = 1$.

According to Sepkoski (1974), a Jaccard index value close to 1 indicates strong co-occurrence between the two binary series, reflecting a high degree of similarity. Conversely, a value close to 0 suggests rare co-occurrence, indicating low similarity.

The Pearson correlation coefficient is used to measure the strength and direction of the linear relationship between the two classes of desertification and the climatic variables (LST, precipitation, and soil moisture) (Wilks 2011). This coefficient, which ranges from -1 to $+1$, allows for the identification of both direct and inverse relationships between variables (Mukaka 2012). A high absolute value of r (close to ± 1) indicates a strong dependency, while a value near 0 suggests the absence of a linear relationship (Bodger 2023). The coefficient r is calculated as follows (eq. 15):

$$r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2 (y_i - \bar{y})^2}} \quad (\text{eq. 15})$$

In this context, x_i and y_i represent the observed values of the climatic variables and desertification levels, respectively, and \bar{x} and \bar{y} are their corresponding means. This correlation analysis thus provides insight into the influence of climatic dynamics on land degradation processes in the Skoura oasis.

3. Results

3.1. Monitoring the level of desertification

This study led to the development of a desertification assessment tool based on a spatial distance approach, with Fig. 9A–D illustrating maps of desertification levels within the study area. Map A, representing the year 1984, reveals a significant expansion of grey and brown zones, indicating moderate to severe

Figure 9. Maps showing the classes of desertification levels. A 1984 B 1996 C 2010 D 2024.

desertification, while green zones, representing non-desertified areas, were primarily concentrated in the northern part of the oasis. By 1996, Map B reveals a substantial portion of the territory appeared in green (no desertification) and light green (low desertification), whereas the brown zones (severe desertification) remained present, although less widespread, particularly in the central area of the oasis. In 2010 (map B) and 2024 (map C), a significant expansion of green zones is observed toward the northern and north-eastern parts of the palm grove, reflecting an improvement in environmental conditions and the presence of non-desertified land. In contrast, the central and southern areas of the oasis experienced a marked progression of severely desertified zones, indicating a spatial intensification of land degradation processes in these regions.

The diagram presents the results expressed as percentages for each desertification class, according to the main temporal milestones. In 1984, a significant trend emerges, with a large proportion of desertified land, representing 24.37% of the total area. This situation is accompanied by a high percentage (38.62) of bare soils, identified as uncultivated land, reflecting an advanced state of environmental degradation at that time. In 1996, a significant percentage of 38.49% of non-desertified land was recorded, contrasting with a substantial decline in the proportion of desertified land. The year 2010 marks a balance between the areas of non-desertified land and those exhibiting severe desertification. By 2024, there is a notable regression in non-desertified land, with only 16.33% remaining, while the percentage of land experiencing severe desertification has increased to 29.9% (Fig. 10).

Figure 10. A diagram displaying the percentage of each desertification class.

3.2. Interannual desertification change

The figure illustrates the interannual evolution of desertification in the study area. The map legend associates green with an improvement in the state of desertification, yellow with areas that have remained stable, and red with sectors that have undergone increased degradation. Between 1984 and 1996 (A), the condition of the Skoura oasis improved significantly throughout the area.

Figure 11. Spatial change of desertification interannual variability. **A** between 1984 and 1996 **B** between 1996 and 2010 **C** between 2010 and 2024. **D** Percentage of Area Change in Desertification Dynamics (1984–2024).

However, between 1996 and 2010 (B), a contrasting dynamic was observed: while the north-eastern and north-western sectors improved, the central part, characterized by the presence of cultivated land and palm trees, underwent a notable deterioration. From 2010 to 2024 (C), the region was subjected to increasing pressures of desertification, affecting the majority of the territory. However, certain localized areas in the northern and north-eastern parts experienced an improvement in their condition (Fig. 11A–C).

Diagram D illustrates the interannual evolution of desertification in the Skoura oasis from 1984 to 2024. During the period 1984–1996, approximately 68% of the territory experienced an improvement, while less than 7% showed signs

Figure 12. The degree of land stabilization in response to desertification processes over the 1984–2024 time series.

of degradation or remained unchanged. Between 1996 and 2010, the trend reversed, with nearly 82% of the area undergoing degradation, around 4% remaining stable, and less than 14% showing improvement. Finally, during the period 2010–2024, although degradation remains predominant at approximately 71%, a slight increase in improved areas is observed (around 21%), along with a stable proportion of unchanged zones at about 8% (Fig. 11D).

3.3. Oasis stability in the face of desertification

The map illustrates the spatiotemporal stability of the lands in the Skoura oasis in the face of desertification dynamics over the period from 1984 to 2024 (Fig. 12). Five stability classes are distinguished. Highly stable, well-protected lands (dark green) occupy a significant portion of the territory, particularly in the north-western and western sectors. Moderately stable lands (olive green) are more diffusely distributed, adjacent to the highly stable areas. In contrast, weakly stabilized lands (beige), subject to episodic desertification, and unstable lands (orange), affected by persistent desertification, predominantly occur in the central and eastern parts of the oasis. Lastly, recently protected lands (light green) appear in localized areas, particularly in the north-east, indicating recent rehabilitation or conservation efforts. This distribution reflects a marked spatial variability in the soil's response to desertification, linked to differentiated environmental and anthropogenic factors.

3.4. Result of correlation

The analysis of temporal similarities between climatic variables and the proportion of non-desertified areas in Skoura reveals a differentiated influence of climatic factors on desertification dynamics (Fig. 13). Land Surface Temperature (LST) exhibits a moderately inverse correlation and opposite similarity (Jaccard Index = 0.63; coincidence rate = 70%; Pearson correlation coefficient: $r = -0.64$), indicating a negative association with non-desertification phases, that is, periods of low LST coincide with a higher proportion of non-desertified areas. Soil moisture stands out with the highest level of co-occurrence (Jaccard = 0.79), its crucial role in ecosystem stabilization. In contrast, precipitation highlighting shows a low similarity (Jaccard = 0.29), suggesting a less direct contribution to soil preservation in the face of desertification.

A marked similarity over the temporal series (Jaccard Index = 0.69; coincidence rate = 72%) is observed between LST and severe desertification, suggesting that higher temperatures coincide with an expansion of areas experiencing extreme soil degradation, likely due to increased evaporation and intensified water stress. The influence of soil moisture appears particularly significant throughout the 40-year study period, with 81% of the time showing that low soil moisture levels coincide with a higher proportion of severely desertified areas, or conversely. In contrast, precipitation exhibits relatively weak co-occurrence and correlation with the severe desertification class (Jaccard Index = 0.37; coincidence rate = 21%; Pearson correlation coefficient = -0.19), suggesting a less direct link with the intensification of the process.

Figure 13. Relationship between desertification classes and climatic data.

3.5. Validation and result accuracy

To assess the reliability of the desertification map produced using the Desertification Monitoring Index (DMI), a random sampling of 300 points was conducted across the entire study area (Fig. 14A). Each point was verified using field observations carried out in 2024, allowing for the identification of the corresponding actual desertification class. For earlier years (1984, 1996, and 2010), due to the lack of ground truth data, visual interpretation was performed using historical imagery available on Google Earth, providing a comparative basis for retrospective validation.

Figure 14. A Validation points and accuracy of the results. **B** Results of the OA and Kappa indices.

The combination of multiple criteria (Table 3) enabled a detailed analysis of the specific characteristics of each sampling point within the oasis. This methodology led to the classification of land into four main categories reflecting the degree of desertification: no desertification, low desertification, advanced desertification, and severe desertification. Additionally, two supplementary categories were defined to identify areas not affected by the desertification process: Miscellaneous and Wasteland.

We evaluated the classification accuracy of the results obtained through our approach using a confusion matrix, which allowed for the calculation of two widely recognized statistical indicators: Overall Accuracy (OA) and Cohen's Kappa coefficient (κ). OA represents the proportion of correctly classified points relative to the total number of points analyzed (Chicco and Jurman 2020). It is calculated using the following formula (eq. 16).

$$OA = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k C_{ii}}{N} \quad (\text{eq. 16})$$

Where: C_{ii} is the number of correctly classified points for class i , and N is the total number of points analyzed.

This measure provides a general indication of the classification model's performance; however, it can be influenced by an unequal distribution of classes. To complement this evaluation, we used Cohen's Kappa coefficient (κ), which accounts for the agreement expected by chance between the predicted classification and the reference data (Pontius and Millones 2011). The formula for Cohen's Kappa is as follows (eq. 17).

$$k = \frac{P_o - P_e}{1 - P_e} \quad (\text{eq. 17})$$

Table 3. The categories and their approved criteria for the validation of our results.

Categories	Field validation criteria
No desertification	Actively maintained and cultivated land. All three vegetation strata are present: (i) herbaceous layer dominated by alfalfa, (ii) shrub layer predominantly composed of olive trees, and (iii) palm layer. Soil exhibits a loose, friable brown texture, indicating good structure and minimal erosion. Boundaries of cultivated plots are clearly identifiable.
Low desertification	Land is partially maintained. Olive trees and date palms remain dominant in the upper strata. The herbaceous layer consists primarily of annual crops, without intercropping practices. Soil is moderately structured, with some compaction in high-traffic areas. Plot boundaries are discernible but may show initial signs of degradation.
Advanced desertification	Land abandoned for >5 years. Sparse olive trees and date palms remain, often showing signs of decline. Herbaceous layer is mostly absent. Boundaries of previously cultivated plots are faint or eroded. Soil is compacted, smooth, with a reflective/shiny surface, indicating reduced porosity and organic matter loss. Signs of initial wind or water erosion may be present.
Severe desertification	Land abandoned for several years. Widespread dieback observed in remaining olive trees and date palms. Vegetation is largely absent; the herbaceous layer is nonexistent. Former plot boundaries are no longer visible. Soil is highly compacted, with a shiny surface, crusting, and possible rill or sheet erosion. Vegetation recovery without intervention is unlikely.
Miscellaneous	Areas not classified under the previous categories, including watercourses, buildings, infrastructure, or other artificial features.
Wasteland	Bare soils with no vegetation cover or evidence of human activity. Often compacted or eroded; may include sand, gravel, or rocky surfaces.

Two proportions of agreement are required: the observed agreement (P_o) and the agreement expected by chance (P_e).

The Kappa index consistently exceeds 0.62, indicating a substantial level of agreement according to the scale proposed by Landis and Koch (1977). This implies that the desertification maps generated using the DMI method demonstrate strong coherence with field observations. The overall accuracy (OA) is generally above 0.78 (Fig. 14B), reflecting a good level of classification accuracy for desertification severity in the Skoura oasis, in accordance with the interpretation guidelines provided by Viera and Garrett (2005).

4. Discussion

The correlation results presented in Fig. 15 highlight the relevance of the MSAVI, Albedo, and SFI indices in modeling the Desertification Monitoring Index (DMI). A strong negative correlation is observed between DMI and MSAVI ($R^2 = 0.9352$), suggesting that increased vegetation cover, as indicated by higher MSAVI values, is closely associated with a significant reduction in desertification levels. Conversely, DMI exhibits a notable positive correlation with both Albedo ($R^2 = 0.667$) and SFI ($R^2 = 0.9015$), indicating that higher surface reflectance and greater soil moisture intensity are linked to more advanced degradation processes. These statistical relationships demonstrate the effectiveness of combining these three biophysical indices to accurately assess and map desertification dynamics in arid environments (Fig. 15).

During the mid-1980s, barren land and areas affected by severe desertification have expanded significantly, covering 62.9% of the oasis surface. This

Figure 15. Correlation between the (DMI) and the MSAVI, Albedo, and SFI indicators.

deterioration is echoed in a study carried out in the Oued Lahdar basin, where vegetation cover fell from 94.3% in 1984 to just 35.4% in 2007, while bare soil increased from 5.7% to 64.6% over the same period (Khalis et al. 2021). Rising temperatures and declining soil moisture have led to widespread drying out and a decline in rosaceous plants, markedly reducing vegetation cover, now confined to the northern, western and eastern parts of the oasis. These dynamics converge with observations made in North African oases, where wind erosion and salinization accelerate soil degradation and impair its organic fertility (King and Thomas 2014). Furthermore, although agricultural expansion has been observed in some regions (such as China between 1987 and 2017), it is often accompanied by a decline in soil moisture and the onset of desertification in some areas, revealing a tension between development and ecological sustainability (Chen et al. 2022).

Between the mid-1980s and the late 1990s, desertification declined—the area of desertified land fell from 15,196 km² to 8,253 km²—indicating a marked improvement in the condition of the oasis and an expansion of vegetated areas, probably favored by milder climatic conditions and the introduction of adapted crops such as olives, corn and alfalfa. This is in line with other observations in Moroccan oasis systems, structured in agro-ecological strata where trees (olive, palm) protect background crops (cereals, alfalfa, vegetables), contributing to resilience in the face of environmental stress (Houssni et al. 2023). However, between 1996 and 2010, desertification intensified—the desertified area climbed to 16,417 km²—due to rising temperatures, falling rainfall and the spread of Bayoud disease, a vascular disease of the date palm that seriously weakens palm groves (Van Praag et al. 2021). Despite this unfavorable context, some areas have miraculously improved thanks to the adoption of modern agricultural systems, illustrating once again the vitality of adaptive strategies in an ecosystem as fragile as the oasis.

Between 2010 and 2024, desertification continued to advance inland from the oasis, causing a significant decline in vegetation, particularly in palm and olive groves. This erosion is the result of a combination of climatic (prolonged drought, rising temperatures), biological and anthropogenic factors. However, some plots in the northern and north-eastern sectors are showing a certain resilience, probably thanks to the implementation of irrigation systems that are more efficient than the traditional khattara network—notably via motorized pumps—or following the adoption of agricultural models better adapted to the constraints of oasis environments (Houssni et al. 2023). These opposing dynamics are set against the backdrop of the second agricultural crisis that hit the Skoura oasis hard, where the gradual abandonment of the khattaras and increased reliance on underground pumping upset the historical balance of the oasis system (Dhawi and Aleidan 2024).

The correlation results show that global warming, combined with soil desiccation, is a major driver of desertification in Skoura, where soil moisture proves to be the most decisive variable – a finding in line with the work of Ait-El-Mokhtar et al. (2021), highlighting the increased vulnerability of Moroccan oases to climatic variations (Bouzelmate et al. 2025). On the other hand, the impact of rainfall appears less clear-cut, suggesting that the resilience or degradation of this ecosystem is highly dependent on the traditional khattara irrigation system and local farming practices. Furthermore, recent national

and institutional initiatives, such as the technological strategies promoted by the National Agency for the Development of Oasis Zones and the Argan Tree (ANDZOA), highlight the importance of innovation in preserving these environments (Chehbouni et al. 2022). On a socio-economic level, pressure on water resources and agricultural degradation are compromising local incomes and community cohesion, while sometimes encouraging migratory dynamics; at the same time, cooperatives and valorization programs are committed to improving environmental governance systems. These dynamics reflect a complexity where climatic, socio-economic and institutional factors are deeply intertwined, validating the urgency of an integrated approach, combining climate modeling, socio-economic data and ecological monitoring, to develop adaptation and sustainable management strategies adapted to this multifactorial context.

5. Conclusion

To enhance the accuracy of desertification monitoring and fully exploit the multidimensional spatial information associated with this phenomenon, this study employed three key indicators, MSAVI, albedo, and SFI to construct a Desertification Monitoring Index (DMI) based on a spatial distance model. The analysis focused on identifying the optimal classification result for desertification and detecting interannual dynamics across the years 1984, 1996, 2010, and 2024. These findings were further compared with previous studies addressing the dual agrarian crisis affecting the Skoura oasis.

The results demonstrate that the DMI effectively integrates the complementary strengths of MSAVI, albedo, and SFI, enabling a more accurate representation of actual desertification levels. Classification performance assessment revealed that the Jenks Natural Breaks method achieved an overall accuracy of 84.21%, indicating its suitability for the study area.

From a spatio-temporal perspective, desertification trends in the Skoura region reveal critical patterns: a marked intensification of land degradation in the mid-1980s associated with the first agrarian crisis; a relative improvement in the late 1990s, characterized by the integration of olive cultivation into the oasis ecosystem; and, over the past decade and a half, a renewed deterioration driven by climatic factors (global warming, prolonged drought), biological threats (notably the spread of Bayoud disease), and socio-environmental pressures. Nevertheless, areas located in the northern and north-eastern parts of the oasis have exhibited relative stability, benefiting from effective conservation measures.

Finally, the correlation analysis underscores a concerning climatic trend: rising temperatures, coupled with declining precipitation and soil desiccation, are key drivers of the intensification of desertification in the Skoura oasis. Considering this, an integrated approach, combining climate modeling, socio-economic data, and ecological monitoring, is essential to refine both adaptation and mitigation strategies in response to this complex and multifaceted challenge.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest was declared.

Ethical statement

No ethical statement was reported.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

Supplementary material 1

Correlation analysis between environmental indices and the Desertification Monitoring Index (DMI)

Authors: Youssef Lassiane

Data type: Microsoft Excel

Explanation note: This section evaluates the correlation between remote sensing indicators and the Desertification Monitoring Index (DMI) to understand their relationships in monitoring land degradation.

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Link: <https://doi.org/10.3897/jbgs.e164548.suppl1>

Supplementary material 2

Correlation between DMI and climatic data

Authors: Youssef Lassiane

Data type: Microsoft Excel

Explanation note: This section analyses the correlation between the Desertification Monitoring Index (DMI) and climatic variables to assess the impact of climate on land degradation dynamics.

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Supplementary material 3

DMI of each polygon in each year

Authors: Youssef Lassiane

Data type: Microsoft Excel

Explanation note: This section present the values of the Desertification Monitoring Index (DMI) calculated for each polygon within the study area, for every year of the analyzed period. These values allow for the assessment of the spatiotemporal evolution of the desertification processes at the local scale.

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